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EXA4MIND

Building the platform for Extreme Data

DEVELOPING A SOLUTION FOR EXTREME DATA THAT
ENABLES ADVANCED DATA ANALYTICS ON SUPERCOMPUTERS
AND AUTOMATED DATA MANAGEMENT

VSB TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA | IT4INNOVATIONS NATIONAL SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER

 Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities

 ORTA DOĞU TEKNİK ÜNİVERSİTESİ
MIDDLE EAST TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

 AUSTRALO

EURAXENT

Valeo

 terraviewos

 CTU
CZECH TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY IN PRAGUE

 Funded by the European Union

alt:nativ

About EXA4MIND

In an age of exponentially growing volumes of data, delivered in vast quantities by business platforms, sensors, simulations, satellites and the media, massive high-performance data analytics are in continuous development. Meanwhile, **Europe's most powerful supercomputers are used for simulations**, and efficient data access is limited to cluster file systems.

The potential power for use in many areas of modern data analytics remains untapped, whilst simultaneously **industry, scientists, and society often struggle to benefit from data pools**.

EXA4MIND will:

Boost common European Big and Extreme Data techniques in science, industry, and SMEs

Leverage existing high-performance data libraries to develop a unified query and indexing system for everybody

Guarantee integrity, and accuracy in the Extreme Data processing

Develop fair, trustworthy AI and data ecosystems

We will build an Extreme Data platform that brings together large scale data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures by implementing novel automated data management and effective data staging. This will enable integration with Extreme Data sources and support complex and advanced data analysis pipelines for knowledge extraction.

Scientific Application Case

Systematic improvement of molecular simulations and accuracy

Industry Application Case

Massively automated annotation & evaluation of automotive camera recordings

SME - Agricultural Application Case

Smart farming/viticulture with sensors & satellite imagery

SME - Health Application Case

Secure data mining in health data